

Call topic: HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01-37

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D7.2: Data Management Plan

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v0.2	October 07, 2024	Anders Eklund (SINTEF), Michalis Georgiades (TALOS)	General specification. Added sample data management.
v0.3	October 17, 2024	Melinda Kuthy (TALOS), Anders Eklund (SINTEF)	Heading numbering. Added storage location for deliverables.
v0.4	October 21, 2024	Martin F. Sunding (SINTEF), Anders Eklund (SINTEF)	QA review and revision.
v1.0	October 31, 2024	Anders Eklund (SINTEF), Spyros Diplas (SINTEF)	Final M6 version.

Publishable Summary

This deliverable is a report that presents the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the MagNEO project. Its purpose is to establish the main elements of the data management policy of the project that will be used by all project partners with regard to the datasets that will be generated during project implementation. While SINTEF will oversee the implementation of policy, the application of this document is the responsibility of all MagNEO project partners. The DMP of the MagNEO project is a living document which will be updated regularly during the execution of the project and will be reported to the Funding Agency at least halfway through the project and at the end of the project.

Abstract

This deliverable is a report that presents the DMP of the MagNEO project. D7.2 is the result of Task 7.4. Its purpose is to establish the main elements of the data management policy of the project that will be used by all project partners with regard to the datasets that will be generated during project implementation.

Data Management Plans are key elements of good data management. DMPs describe the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by a Horizon Europe project. They also support the European Commission's goal to advance Open Science policy and practices. Finally, to ensure the availability and utility of project research data, DMPs outline the

measures that will be taken to maximise access and re-use of the data for further purposes and applications.

The DMP of the MagNEO project will cover the types of data and research outputs, the compliance with the FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), and the way in which data will be stored and preserved. While SINTEF will oversee the implementation of policy, the application of this document is the responsibility of all MagNEO partners.

The DMP is a living document which will be updated regularly during the execution of the project whenever significant changes arise, such as (but not limited to) new data, changes in consortium policies (e.g. new innovation potential, decision to file for a patent), changes in consortium composition and external factors (e.g. new consortium members joining or old members leaving). The DMP will be updated regularly during the execution of the project, and reported to the Funding Agency at least halfway through the project and at the end of the project.

Glossary

Term	Explanation
APC	Article Publishing Charge
AAM	Author Accepted Manuscript
CC 0	Creative Common Public Domain Dedication
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
PU	Public
SEN	Sensitive
VoR	Version of Record
WP	Work Package

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1. Data Management Plan

1.1 Introduction

DMPs are key elements of good data management. DMPs describe the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/ or generated by a Horizon Europe project. They also support the European Commission's goal to advance Open Science policy and practices [1]. Finally, to ensure the availability and utility of the project's research data, they outline the measures that will be taken to maximise access and re-use of the data for further purposes and applications.

MagNEO DMP aims to plan the life cycle of data within the project. It offers a long-term perspective by outlining how data will be generated, collected, documented, shared, preserved and deleted within the project. It is a key element in ensuring that data is managed properly to support knowledge discovery and innovation. Contemporary e-Science requires data to be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable in the long-term [2].

The DMP will be regularly revised throughout the project, to contribute to the good data management and to optimize transparency and data usage. The DMP will describe what data MagNEO will generate or collect, storing and handling of datasets, whether and how data will be exploited or made accessible for verification and reuse, as well as how data will be curated and preserved. For this purpose, the following categories are defined: Research data, Other Research Output and Personal data. In addition, different openness levels are established: Public (PU) and Sensitive (SEN). Furthermore, the DMP will give instructions on naming conventions and metadata structures. Ethical issues affecting data sharing and security arrangements for chosen platforms and repositories will be defined.

MagNEO will support reproducibility by uploading the data and metadata needed to validate results of the scientific publications to a trusted open repository e.g., Zenodo.

1.2 Data Summary

As for the purpose of data collection and generation, only data that is needed to perform project activities will be collected, and as far as possible, participants will not be asked to provide personal data unless this is necessary.

In the framework of the MagNEO project, the types of data that will be generated include:

1. **Data generated from open accessible information** such as reports or databases
2. **Data generated by project partners and external evaluator activities**, such as deliverables, technical documents, meeting minutes and other work carried out to achieve the objectives of the MagNEO project.

Additionally, the MagNEO project will collect, generate and reuse various types of data, such as:

- Calculation data (data from models, simulations, and other calculations)
- Experimental data (data from production/processing and characterization, results from controlled trials or test data)
- Observations and collected data
 - Survey/interview/transcript data
 - Literature Measuring sequences, code
- Algorithms, scripts
- Audio-visual data
- Physical objects (samples, artefacts)

These data can be in the form of raw and processed data.

MagNEO will primarily use widely accepted formats for data generation, such as:

- Documents/Reports/Publications: .PDF/A, txt, doc/docx, odp
- Spreadsheets: xls/xlsx, cvs, ods
- Databases: SQL or MySQL
- Audio files: .mp3, .wav, .wma, .ra
- Pictures: jpg, png, tiff
- Video: avi, flv, mov, mp4, wmv

Raw data storage might, however, require other data formats to ensure complete information preservation. In this case it is advised to store the data both in a raw format and a widely accepted format.

The estimated size of the data is:

- 1 TB – 100 TB

Shared research data (i.e. outside the MagNEO consortium) will not include trade secrets, commercial information, materials necessary to be held confidential by researchers until they are published, or security sensitive information.

Sharing of working documents and outcomes of the MagNEO work with external stakeholders depends on security and commercial sensitivity of information they contain.

1.3 Versions and updates

The Data Management Plan has been developed according to the project work plan. The DMP is a living document which will be updated regularly during the execution of the project and whenever significant changes arise, such as the availability of new data sources, changes in consortium policies (e.g. new innovation potential, decision to file for a patent), changes in consortium composition (e.g. new members joining or old members leaving), any other reason that might be of relevance to the project. The DMP will be updated at least halfway through the project (M24) and at the end of the project (M48).

1.4 Data storage

1.4.1 MagNEO SharePoint

The project collaborative platform – MagNEO SharePoint – was set up by SINTEF (Figure 1 and Figure 2). It is available at: <https://sintef.sharepoint.com/teams/work-24047>

This platform is a central hub for project management and a secure tool for the storage and sharing of documents and all project information. It ensures a convenient, reliable and flexible framework for project collaboration, internal communication, monitoring and reporting. The Sharepoint site will be the project's online working and collaboration area during the 48 months the project is active.

Access is managed by SINTEF and is secured by individual usernames and passwords. All requests for access are sent directly to SINTEF which verifies that the sender is employed by one of the partner organisations. Also, there is a project contact list (Excel file) saved on SharePoint.

Figure 1 MagNEO SharePoint homepage

All partners will be responsible for uploading datasets they have collected/generated during the project. Each dataset will be catalogued in an Excel workbook providing an overview of all datasets in the project, as well as uploaded to a dedicated research data folder in the SharePoint site. All datasets will use standard SharePoint version control and additional access control is available to enable limited access to certain types of data.

These metadata will be provided for each data set:

- Dataset name
- Description
- Origin of data
- WP number
- Task or deliverable number (if applicable)

- File format(s)
- Responsible institution (Data owner)
- Contact person
- Dissemination level
- Comments (if applicable)

General Principles

- All partners have the same level of information.
- Contacts: partners are requested to keep their own data up-to-date and update the contact list when necessary.
- Documents – a unique and centralised version is available to all partners:
 - Full security of data is provided.
 - Multiple versions are avoided to prevent confusion.
Note: old versions are either deleted or moved to a sub-folder 'Old'.
 - Co-editing of MS Office documents is possible for convenience and time efficiency.
 - Partners are requested to use the Track Changes mode, especially in the review process of minutes and deliverables.
 - For deliverables, the versioning function allows tracing back of document elaboration and retrieval of possible errors.
 - The Delete function should only be used to delete files (this sends them to the Recycle Bin where from they can be retrieved in case of afterthought).
- No documents sent by email:
 - Emails are not secure.
 - Attachments will overload inboxes and heavy attachments can't be sent by email.
 - Documents should be worked out in the platform.
 - Links (or the pathway) should be sent by email to notify other partners.
 - Local versions should be avoided as much as possible.
 - Partners inform each other proactively when new documents are uploaded to SharePoint and when changes are made to existing documents.

Figure 2 MagNEO SharePoint structure

- For all WPs focusing on research, development, and innovation, there is a folder '03 Scientific - Technical', and there are sub-folders for each WP to ease collaborative work.
- General Information, Reporting, Scientific-Technical, Dissemination-Publication, Meetings, Exploitation, Amendments, Templates, and Dissemination Material have their own folder.
- Templates for meeting minutes and deliverables are saved in folder 08 Templates.

1.4.2 MagNEO Zenodo open access repository

MagNEO will use Zenodo, a trusted and OpenAire compliant repository to comply with the FAIR principles. All scientific publications, including public deliverables and public parts of underlying datasets will be uploaded to the MagNEO Community in the repository. In addition, the project will upload other datasets (not directly linked to publications and deliverables) with dissemination level "Public" and make them openly accessible via the repository.

For each submission, Zenodo assigns a persistent digital object identifier (DOI) to publicly available documents to make content uniquely and easily citeable. MagNEO Zenodo repository is accessible at: <https://zenodo.org/communities/magneo> (Figure 3).

Figure 3 MagNEO Zenodo homepage

1.4.3 Instructions for uploading datasets to project platform and chosen repository

Table 1 and Figure 4 provide instructions to project participants on how to upload datasets to SharePoint and Zenodo:

Upload instructions – MagNEO Sharepoint Site
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Go to the dataset folder in the MagNEO Sharepoint site: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Documents/Shared consortium/10 Datasets ○ Link (clickable): https://sintef.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/teams/work-24047/Delte%20dokumenter/Shared%20consortium/10%20Datasets?csf=1&web=1&e=yWG72U • Create a sub-directory for your dataset using the naming convention (for details see 2.1.1): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ WP4_LCA Reports ○ WP5 T5.1_ABS Systems • Upload the data files into your sub-directory • Add/update mandatory metadata in this workbook: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ https://sintef.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/teams/work-24047/Delte%20dokumenter/Shared%20consortium/10%20Datasets/WP7%20T7.4_List%20of%20datasets%20and%20other%20research%20outputs?csf=1&web=1&e=bFVJSN
Upload instructions – Data Repository
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research data underlying scientific publications/classified as "Public" should, in addition, be uploaded to Zenodo. To do this you must complete the following steps: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Prepare a copy of your dataset as a single .zip file with a version number in its name, following this naming convention (i.e. ending with e.g. "_v1.zip"): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ WP4_LCA Reports_v1.zip ▪ WP5 T5.1_ABS Systems_v4.zip ○ Store the dataset .zip file in this Sharepoint folder: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Documents/Shared consortium/10 Datasets/Zipped versions ○ Create a personal profile in Zenodo to be able to upload files ○ Click on the <i>MagNEO Community</i> link above, or search for "MagNEO" under the "Communities" tab at the top of the Zenodo site ○ On the Community site, click the green "New upload" button in the top right corner ○ Enter requested data and confirm the upload. ○ Remember to add the EU Open Research Repository community in the box labelled "communities". You can use the search function to locate the community and add it. The data will then automatically be included in both communities, so you don't have to do it twice. • Uploading should be done as soon as possible and at the latest on article publication or EC approval of deliverables for underlying datasets. Other datasets will be uploaded in the final month of the project at the latest. • Each partner is responsible for uploading data sets collected/generated by them. If needed, PROJECT data manager will supply assistance.

Table 1 Instructions for uploading datasets to SharePoint

Figure 4 Process for uploading datasets

1.4.4 Documentation of samples

Physical samples that have been used to produce the dataset shall be documented in an Excel workbook file (Figure 5). This file shall be included in the dataset. MagNEO will typically handle physical samples in several steps of processing (from powder to additively manufactured magnets), and different partners will be involved along this processing chain. All physical samples will be named, in order to keep track of their provenance. Each partner may utilize their own naming scheme for the samples that they handle.

The Excel workbook should preferably also include data about the samples. By supplying this, it will be possible to easily identify samples that are of interest based on their processing conditions and/or characterization results. It will also be easy to find the most important data about the samples when backtracing the provenance of a particular sample of interest.

Contents of a Samples.xlsx file:

- Mandatory columns:
 - Origin (the organization that supplied the sample)
 - Original name (of the sample at the original organization)
 - Sample (The name or ID of the sample that is used in this dataset)
- Optional columns (recommended):
 - Processing conditions utilized for the sample
 - Characterization results
 - Other information

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
1													
2	Origin	Original name	Sample	Comment	path to images	Shape	Embed	Prep	location	direction	Sent to	Sent date	
3	Magneti	ALNiCo5 DG	R01	BHmax=50	HEU MagNEO - R01 - Alle dokumenter (sharepoint.com)	cylinder							
4	Magneti	AINiCo8 casted	R02		HEU MagNEO - R02 - Alle dokumenter (sharepoint.com)								
5	Magneti	AINiCo8 sintered	R03		HEU MagNEO - R03 - Alle dokumenter (sharepoint.com)								
6	Magneti	AINiCo5 DG casted	R04		HEU MagNEO - R04 - Alle dokumenter (sharepoint.com)								
7	SINTEF	S01	S01		HEU MagNEO - S01-S03 - Alle dokumenter (sharepoint.com)	Button	PolyFast	Prep1					
8	SINTEF	S02	S02			Button	PolyFast	Prep1					
9	SINTEF	S03	S03			Button	PolyFast	Prep1					
10		R01	R01ct		HEU MagNEO - R01 - Alle dokumenter (sharepoint.com)		PolyFast	Prep1	center	tangential			
11		R01	R01cz		HEU MagNEO - R01 - Alle dokumenter (sharepoint.com)		PolyFast	Prep1	center	along z			
12		R01	R01et		HEU MagNEO - R01 - Alle dokumenter (sharepoint.com)		PolyFast	Prep1	edge	tangential			
13		R01	R01ez		HEU MagNEO - R01 - Alle dokumenter (sharepoint.com)		PolyFast	Prep1	edge	along z			
14		R01	R01x				no	no			UIO	20.06.2024	
15	Magneti	AINiCo5-7	R05	BHmax=61	HEU MagNEO - R05 - Alle dokumenter (sharepoint.com)	cylinder a=37mm, h=5mm	no	Prep2					
16		R05	R05a	cut from R05		cap thicness 5mm					SINTEF/TEM		
17		R05	R05b	cut from R05		slice width 6 mm							
18		R05	R05c	cut from R05		half slice about 5x14 mm					UIO	15.08.2024	
19		R05	R05d	cut from R05		Half + cylinder							
20	SINTEF	S01	S01a	cut from S01	S01-S03	Half button	PolyFast						
21	SINTEF	S02	S02a	cut from S02	S01-S03	Half button	PolyFast						
22	SINTEF	S03	S03a	cut from S03	S01-S03	Half button	PolyFast						
23		S04	S04a	cut from S04	S04-S07-S10-S13	Half button	PolyFast	Prep2					
24		S07	S07a	cut from S07	S04-S07-S10-S13	Half button	PolyFast	Prep2					
25		S10	S10a	cut from S10	S04-S07-S10-S13	Half button	PolyFast	Prep2					
26		S13	S13a	cut from S13	S04-S07-S10-S13	Half button	PolyFast	Prep2					
27													

Figure 5 MagNEO Samples.xlsx file

1.5 Open dissemination strategy

During the Project and for a period of 1 year after the end of the Project, any type of dissemination of own Results by one or several Parties including but not restricted to publications and presentations, shall be governed by the procedure of Article 17.4 of the Grant Agreement and its Annex 5, Section Dissemination, subject to the following provisions. These procedures apply to for example conference abstracts, presentations and publications and state the sending of prior written notice, possible objections and their required time frames.

MagNEO partners will aim for fast and open access publication and have identified Zenodo as an appropriate platform for open access sharing of publications (see section 1.4.2).

In addition, some of the research partners may have dedicated budgets to publish in open access journals according to the gold open access model whereby the Version of Record (VoR) is permanently and freely available online for anyone, anywhere to read. An article publishing charge (APC) is usually applicable.

If for some reason (e.g. budget dedicated to open access journals entirely used), open access will be given according to the green open access model whereby an earlier version of the manuscript (the Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM)) is deposited in an online trusted repository (e.g. Zenodo). The publication will be shared without having to pay an APC. No embargo period will be applied, immediate open access will be granted.

Finally, public deliverables, communication materials (presentations, news, videos, etc.) will be made available to a wide audience of stakeholders on the MagNEO website: <https://www.magneoproject.eu>

1.6 Protection of personal data

According to article 4 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Regulation 2016/679), ‘personal data’ means “any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.”[3]), ‘personal data’ means “any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity of that natural person.”

As set out in Article 15.2 of the Grant Agreement, MagNEO partners will “process personal data under the Agreement in compliance with the applicable EU, international and national law on data protection (in particular, Regulation 2016/679).

They will ensure that personal data is:

- processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subjects
- collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes
- adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed
- accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date
- kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the data is processed and
- processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the data.”

The partners may grant their personnel access to personal data only if it is strictly necessary for implementing, managing and monitoring the Agreement. The beneficiaries must ensure that the personnel are under a confidentiality obligation.

Personal data collection will be limited in scope and will include the minimum needed to:

- Implement, manage and monitor the Grant Agreement
- Establish the required collaboration among the project partners and external partners, such as the MagNEO Stakeholder Group or Cluster Community.

All personal data will be securely stored on MagNEO SharePoint.

2. FAIR data

Throughout and after the project, the MagNEO project will abide by the FAIR [4] guiding principles for scientific data management and stewardship, with FAIR standing for Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (see Table 2 below [5]).

Principle	Explanation
Findability	Datasets should be described, identified and registered or indexed in a clear and unequivocal manner
Accessibility	Datasets should be accessible through a clearly defined access procedure, ideally using automated means. Metadata should always remain accessible
Interoperability	Data and metadata are conceptualised, expressed and structured using common, published standards
Reusability	Characteristics of data and their provenance are described in detail according to domain- relevant community standards, with clear and accessible conditions for use

Table 2 The meaning of the FAIR principles

This chapter will describe the project’s adherence to these principles in more detail.

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

The MagNEO consortium as a whole will communicate and implement together good practices to provide the most successful outcomes in terms of data management. While SINTEF will oversee the implementation of policy, each WP leader is responsible for the data generated within their respective WP (see section 4).

To ensure adherence to the principles of FAIR data and provide the necessary measures for data security, the following sections explain the overarching procedures which must be followed during the duration of the project in addition to partners’ internal rules.

In order to be findable, a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI) will be assigned to the data, and rich metadata describing the data will be searchable and available online. Further detailed information on metadata for scientific publications and research data is provided in section 2.4.

2.1.1 MagNEO SharePoint dataset names

To ensure that the data produced during the project is easily findable on MagNEO SharePoint, the consortium partners have established the following internal procedures.

When storing data, the following naming conventions must be followed regardless of the nature of the dataset: if the data refers to the WP, case 1 applies; if the dataset refers to a specific task within a WP, case 2 applies. If a dataset is specifically created for use in a deliverable, case 3 applies.

- Case 1: WPX_Dataset Name

For example:

- WP1_HEA compositions
- WP4_LCA Reports
- WP5_minutes

- Case 2: WPX TX.X_Dataset Name

For example:

- WP2 T2.1_CFD Simulations
- WP5 T5.1_ABS Systems
- WP7 T7.5_minutes

- Case 3: WPX DX.X_Dataset Name

For example:

- WP1 D1.3_HEA computed data
- WP3 D3.2_Large powder batch data

2.1.2 MagNEO Deliverables

All MagNEO deliverables will be identified with a unique and persistent numeric identifier: MagNEO - Document description (e.g. MagNEO – D7.2 Data Management Plan).

Basic metadata will be used to facilitate the retrieval of information by partners (Figure 6):

- Logo, Long Title, Call topic, Grant Agreement number,
- Deliverable number and title with the correct naming convention
- Lead Author(s), Contributors and Reviewers
- EU logo and disclaimer

Call topic: HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01-TWO-STAGE
Grant Agreement n° 101130095

D[X.X]: [Title of the Deliverable]

Lead Author: [Name and organisation]

with contributions from: [Name and organisation]

•

Reviewed by [Names and organisations]

Deliverable nature	
Dissemination level	
Contractual delivery date	
Actual delivery version	

Version history

Version	Date	Editors	Description

Figure 6 MagNEO deliverable template cover page

MagNEO deliverables will be versioned. To this end, the project deliverable template includes a version (see Table 3). Partners will identify different versions by using a two-digit version number (i.e. vX.X). Once the author(s) address(es) reviewers’ comments, the Coordinator will carry out a formal check before submission. After approval by the EU services, the Coordinator will upload the final version to the relevant folder on SharePoint.

Version	Date	Editors	Description
1.0	DD/MM/YYYY	Name – Org. short	Initial Version
2.0			[Ex. Edited table 1]
...			[Ex. Added subsection 1.2.]
Final			Final Version

Table 3 Version history of MagNEO deliverables

The deliverable type has four options: R – Document, Report; DMP – Data Management Plan; DEM – Demonstrator; OTHER.

The dissemination level has two possibilities: PU – Public; SEN – Sensitive as per Article 13 of the Grant Agreement. Out of the 28 deliverables listed in the Grant Agreement, 8 are public while 20 are classified as sensitive.

All deliverables are stored in the **Shared consortium/02 Reporting** directory on the MagNEO Sharepoint. Public deliverables will also be published in the MagNEO Zenodo community.

- Deliverables in progress:
 - **Shared consortium/02 Reporting/01 Reports in progress/01 Deliverables**
 - <https://sintef.sharepoint.com/teams/work-24047/Delte%20dokumenter/Forms/AllItems.aspx?id=%2Fteams%2Fwork%2D24047%2FDelte%20dokumenter%2FShared%20consortium%2F02%20Reporting%2F01%20Reports%20in%20progress%2F01%20Deliverables&viewid=d70af837%2Dc345%2D487c%2D9a1d%2D11e7bbd2bdf9>
- Submitted deliverables:
 - **Shared consortium/02 Reporting/02 Final reports/01 Deliverables**
 - <https://sintef.sharepoint.com/teams/work-24047/Delte%20dokumenter/Forms/AllItems.aspx?id=%2Fteams%2Fwork%2D24047%2FDelte%20dokumenter%2FShared%20consortium%2F02%20Reporting%2F02%20Final%20reports%2F01%20Deliverables&viewid=d70af837%2Dc345%2D487c%2D9a1d%2D11e7bbd2bdf9>

2.2 Making data accessible

Accessible data means that humans and machines should be able to access it under specific conditions or restrictions where appropriate. To take into consideration concerns related to intellectual property rights, personal data protection and confidentiality, security and legitimate commercial interest, not all data will be open. However, even when the data will not be accessible, metadata will be FAIR, accessible wherever possible, in compliance with the principle of “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”.

Public deliverables and communication materials will be made available on the project website, under the tab ‘Resources’. An abstract of scientific publications accompanied by hyperlinks to the journal websites will also be featured in this section of the website.

Zenodo, a well-established repository, will be used to store project results and their metadata, so that they are provided with persistent identifiers. Adequate metadata schemes will be selected, and metadata will be published on Zenodo (see section 1.4.2). No specific software tools will be needed to access the data.

MagNEO website will not share any sensitive or confidential information. Such data will be available only on MagNEO SharePoint.

Processing of personal data that will be collected and processed during the MagNEO project will follow the key principles of the GDPR: lawfulness, fairness and transparency; purpose limitation; data minimisation; accuracy; storage limitation; integrity and confidentiality (security); accountability.

The Table below provides a list of datasets expected to be generated in the MagNEO project and their planned accessibility. This list constitutes the first version of dataset description, and we recognise that

it will develop and grow as the project evolves. In addition, some information concerning the datasets currently remain unknown, e.g. size of the datasets. An updated version of the list containing all dataset details will be provided at the end of the project.

WP	Dataset name	Description/Purpose	Format	Responsible	(PU/SEN)	Comments
WP1	DED-LB/Mp composition screening	Data coming for using DED-LB/Mp printing and characterization related with achieving the best snisotropic microstructure	.Jpeg, .xlsx, docs,	AIMEN	SEN	To be discussed if part of the data obtained can be made public to publish datasets in ZENODO (valuable for the EC)
WP1	DED-LB/Mp AlNiCo5 printing	Data related with the printing of AlNiCo 5 to be compared with current manufacturing technologies	. Jpeg, .xlsx, docs,	AIMEN	SEN	To be discussed if part of the data obtained can be made public to publish datasets in ZENODO (valuable for the EC)
WP1	Electronic structure data	VASP and SIESTA input and output files (energies, structures, wavefunctions)	Pure text and binaries	SIN	SEN	
WP1	List of samples	List of samples produced using arcmlter, with their composition	.xlsx	SIN	SEN	
WP1	Images of samples	Microscopy images of samples	.tiff	SIN	SEN	
WP1	Input data to atomistic spin dynamics	Exchange coefficients, anisotropies	text	SIN	SEN	
WP1	Input data to micromagnetic modelling		text	SIN	SEN	
WP1	X-ray diffraction data	Phase characterization data for CALPHAD validation	.xrdml, pdf	VTT	SEN	
WP1	Phase diagrams & composition profiles	CALPHAD simulation results	.png .jpg or other images	VTT	SEN	
WP2	Proprietary CFD simulation results of the gas atomization process	Numerical domains, meshes and simulation results of the industrial-scale atomization unit. Improved designs of critical componentes and proposal of new anti-satellite systems. Advanced multiphase modelling procedures to simulate the	.step, .scdoc, .msh, .cas, .dat, .xlsx, .txt, .jpgs	CEIT	SEN	The eventual results of these studies will be publishable in scientific journals.

		fragmentation and the solidification of the droplets.				
WP2	Additive manufacturing simulations	List of simulations of the AM process for the different case studies. It includes for each case: the simulation input, material properties, simulation output and possible script for pre- and post-processing	.txt, .csv, proprietary format	SINTEF	SEN	
WP2	Grain structure data	List of measurements for the characterization of the grain structure as a function of material and process parameters	.txt, .jpg, proprietary format	SINTEF	SEN	
WP2	Proprietary simulation results data generated from commercial software	Permanent magnet drive models. Modelling of motor performance and efficiency	.mot	3DC	SEN	The input data contains the detailed technical information of the end-users as input. The models will be used to study the effect of different factors, such as changing the magnet properties. The result of simulations is not a tabulated data to be stored in other forms. It is a heatmap data on the design that requires the proprietary software to read and analyse it. The eventual results of these studies will be publishable in scientific journals.
WP3	Full characterization report of gas atomized powders produced in the laboratory and industrial scale atomization units	Chemical, physical, thermal, microstructural, and magnetic properties of the resulting gas atomized powders	,pdf, .xlsx, .tif, .txt	CEIT	SEN	Includes operational conditions and components used in the gas atomization experiments.
WP3	PBF-LB optimization results (D3.3)	A dataset listing all the PBF-LB experiments conducted: the PBF-LB process parameters and corresponding results (i.e. porosity, cracking)	.xlsx, .tiff	VTT / CONIFY	SEN	The "combined" dataset with input / output from the optimization experiments will be an .xlsx file. OM images from sample cross-

		from the PBF-LB experiments conducted on the selected alloys.				sections (.tiff or jpeg images) will be the "raw-data" set from which the results i.e. -% porosity and presence of cracking or other unwanted defects will be quantified. Python or similar may be used to draw visual processing maps by fitting data from the experiments to appropriate models to find the optimum combination of processing parameters. The results will be part of D3.3 and targeted for journal publications
WP3	Production data for thermoplastic-bonded magnets (HEAs)	Data on the production of polymer-bonded filaments and granulates	CSV and/or Excel and/or PDF	AIM	SEN	Includes processing parameters and material compositions
WP3	Magnetic alignment data for thermoplastic-bonded magnets (HEAs)	Data on the effectiveness of in-situ magnetic alignment during the FFF/FPF-AM process.	CSV and/or Excel and/or PDF	AIM	SEN	Includes experimental matrix details and temperature monitoring
WP3	Coupon test data for thermoplastic-bonded magnets (HEAs)	Magnetic and mechanical properties of manufactured coupons	CSV and/or Excel and/or PDF	AIM	SEN	Data informs on the optimum AM processing parameters for improved magnetic properties
WP3	Recycling for thermoplastic-bonded magnets (AlNiCo)	Data from composite filaments and pellets production, characterization results of produced materials and 3d printed coupons	PDF, .png, .tif, .jpeg, .doc, .csv	BioG3D	SEN	
WP4	LCA & LCC analysis	Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) & Life Cycle Costing (LCC) analysis to evaluate environmental and economic impacts, using tools like SimaPro and Excel-based models	xlsx, csv	IRES	SEN	
WP4	Socio-technical analysis (STA)	Socio-technical analysis (STA) focusing on the systemic interactions and social acceptance of innovations using a technological innovation systems (TIS) framework	xlsx, csv, pdf	SIN	PU	

WP4	Techno-economic analyses (TEA)	Techno-economic analysis (TEA) to estimate build time, cost efficiency, and process optimization for the LPBF of ALNiCo and HEA applied to end-user cases	.pdf, .doc, .xlsx, .txt, .csv	SLM	SEN	
WP4	Strategies for recycling	Development of recycling strategies, including material collection, waste assessment, and the remelting and reuse of alloys	xlsx, csv, pdf	SIN	SEN	
WP5	Sample information	Microscopy images, measurement data (roughness, density, conductivity, mechanical properties)	.xlsx, .csv, .png, .jpeg, .tif, .pdf	SLM	SEN	
WP5	Build job information	sample geometries, process parameters, sensor logs	.xlsx, .csv, .pdf, .slm, .magics	SLM	SEN	
WP5	Statistical Analysis Results	Material Process Development will be conducted using statistical DoE and analysis resulting in statistical models and indicators	.xlsx, .ppt, .html, .jmp	SLM	SEN	
WP7	List of datasets and other research outputs	List of the datasets and other research outputs (samples, computer code, models, demonstrators etc.) that will be produced in MagNEO. Publications are not to be included in this list (but will be built upon these items).	.xlsx	SINTEF	SEN	The list of datasets and other research outputs, i.e. the information in this document, will be included in the PUBLIC deliverable D7.2 Data Management Plan (therein excluding the names of the contact persons).

Table 4 Types of Datasets

2.3 Making data interoperable

Data and metadata generated by partners will conform to recognised formats and standards to allow them to be combined and exchanged: preference will be given to open and widely used formats such as csv, xlsx, txt, jpg, tiff, docx, pdf, etc. Readme files (*.txt) will accompany data and metadata.

To ensure interoperability of data, the MagNEO project will deliver and share data through its Zenodo repository. Indeed, Zenodo uses JSON Schema as internal representation of metadata and offers export to other popular formats such as Dublin Core or MARCXML. This JSON Schema, which is defined and used by Zenodo, facilitates technical and syntactical interoperability when working with the metadata that we as users supply to Zenodo during dataset upload (usually by entering the requested information in the fields on the upload web page). The Zenodo JSON Schema has fields to express the metadata of the *dataset* (e.g. DOI, license, contributors and language). The primary available location for metadata about the actual *data* (e.g. scientific method and parameter ranges) is the Description text field. Throughout the MagNEO project, the partners will apply specific metadata standards by including such files in the dataset and mentioning them in the Description field. It will be an on-going effort to identify applicable, specific metadata standards for the various types of data that will be handled during the project.

MagNEO partners will be responsible for storing all data in the appropriate format that will make data accessible to all professionals and end users who might be interested in exploiting the data generated during the project.

2.4 Increase data re-use

Since a lot of documentation is needed to support data interpretation and reuse, MagNEO data will conform to community norms and be clearly licenced so that others know what kinds of re-use are permitted. MagNEO partners will make sure that the data is accurate and well described, and the data generated will have a clear and accessible data usage licence. The data description (including the methodology used to obtain the data) and license will be included in the dataset Readme file (also mentioned in section 2.3). If the Readme file refers to other documents with more detailed data descriptions, these are also to be included in the dataset.

- Scientific publications: metadata of deposited publications will be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue); Horizon Europe funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata will include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tool and instrument needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.
- Research data: metadata of deposited data must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s),

venue and embargo); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.

Data re-use before publication and re-use of data during and after the end of the project will be possible according to the provisions set out in the Consortium Agreement. Sharing of working documents and outcomes of the MagNEO work with external stakeholders will depend on security and commercial sensitivity of information they contain.

The Consortium will maintain project data in a reusable state for as long as possible after the end of the project. An initial availability period of 5 years is foreseen. This duration may change depending on agreements and future discussions among partners.

3. Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, MagNEO partners will also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, samples, demonstrators, etc.).

MagNEO partners will consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

4. Allocation of resources

Costs related to data management and data storage are at partners' own cost. While SINTEF will oversee the implementation of policy, the application of this document is the responsibility of all MagNEO project partners.

More specifically, WP leaders are responsible for:

- Implementing of the data management policy in their respective WPs.
- Monitoring data management activities and deadlines and sending reminders to partners.
- Offering customised help and further guidance for using MagNEO's living DMP.
- Asking partners for missing information or clarifications.
- Providing input to the DMP deliverable documents by analysing and summarising the WP-specific datasets listed in MagNEO's living DMP.

- Monitoring that open results (data and software) are deposited in MagNEO Zenodo repository and sending reminders to partners.
- Contacting the Coordinator in case of questions and ethical and privacy issues that may forbid publication of the data.
- Ensuring that the metadata of data used and produced at work package level is made available in MagNEO's living DMP according to the MagNEO data management policy and guidelines in a timely manner.

The project website, which is managed by TALOS, will be maintained for a period of 1 year after project completion. Maintenance is already included in the one-time payment made to web-developers during the website creation. As for the domain name, the subscription is a 5-year plan (4 + 1 years after the end) and costs are not significant.

MagNEO SharePoint, which is managed by SINTEF, will be maintained for a period of 5 year after the project end.

5. Data Security

The project's data sharing and storing infrastructure – MagNEO SharePoint – is protected from unauthorised access and ensures the security and protection of all sensitive data during the whole project period and beyond as it is managed by SINTEF. Access is only granted upon request to people employed by partner organisations. Each partner organisation is responsible for informing the project coordinator whenever people leave their organization, so that their SharePoint access can be removed. MagNEO SharePoint also provides data recovery functionalities to avoid accidental loss of data.

MagNEO Zenodo open access repository provides secure short-term and long-term storage of the research data since it stores data safely in CERN's cloud infrastructure. "All files uploaded to Zenodo are stored in CERN's EOS service in an 18 petabytes disk cluster. Each file copy has two replicas located on different disk servers. Metadata and persistent identifiers in Zenodo are stored in a PostgreSQL instance operated on CERN's Database on Demand infrastructure with 12-hourly backup cycle with one backup sent to tape storage once a week" [6].

6. Ethics

The proposed work in MagNEO will fully comply with the regulations set out in Regulation (EU) 2016/679, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [7]. In addition, MagNEO complies with the principles of the European Charter for Researchers, the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, including ethical standards and guidelines, regardless of the country in which research is carried out.

Nothing in this project shall be deemed to require a party to breach any mandatory statutory law under which the party is operating. This includes any national or European regulations, rules and norms regarding ethics in conducting research.

SINTEF follows the Vancouver Recommendations for publication of scientific work.

Among others, the MagNEO project will abide by the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and its good research practices in the following contexts: research environment; training, supervision and mentoring; research procedures; safeguards; data practices and management; collaborative working; publication, dissemination and authorship; reviewing and assessment [8].

The MagNEO project does not involve human participants as research objects or the collection and processing of personal data. None of the planned activities will be carried out in non-EU countries.

6.1 Contact information

Use of e-mail addresses in MagNEO SharePoint Site:

An e-mail address is by definition personal information and covered by GDPR. The e-mail addresses of project participants are stored in the MagNEO SharePoint Site. Only the project participants invited will have access. The e-mail address is a prerequisite to access the projects working area. By accepting the SharePoint invitation the participants consent to use and store their e-mail address for the purpose of online collaboration in the project.

The email-addresses will be deleted when access to the project area is no longer needed (1 year after project closure).

SINTEF has signed GDPR data processing agreements with both Microsoft and the IT operations contractor handling our SharePoint platform.

7. Other issues

Not applicable at this stage.

8. Conclusion

This deliverable presents the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the MagNEO project as defined in the first months of the project. Its purpose is to establish the main elements of the data management policy of the project that will be used by all project partners with regard to all the datasets that will be generated during project implementation.

The DMP of the MagNEO project covers the types of data/research outputs, the compliance with the FAIR data principles, and the way in which data will be stored and preserved. While SIN will oversee

the implementation of policy, the application of this document is the responsibility of all MagNEO project partners.

The DMP is a living document which will be updated regularly during the execution of the project whenever significant changes arise, such as (but not limited to) new data, changes in consortium policies (e.g. new innovation potential, decision to file for a patent), changes in consortium composition and external factors (e.g. new consortium members joining or old members leaving). The DMP will be updated at least halfway through the project and at the end of the project.

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